

A STUDY ON HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS' ACHIEVEMENTS IN ECONOMICS

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Cite This Article: Dr. M. Rajakumar, "A Study on Higher Secondary Students' Achievements in Economics", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 2, Issue 2, Page Number 279-281, 2017.

Abstract:

This study examined the achievement of higher secondary school students of Tirunelveli District. The sample consists of 460 males and 600 females in higher secondary schools of Tirunelveli District in Tamil Nadu. Achievement test in Economics for higher secondary school students constructed by the investigator was used for data collection. The mean value of Achievement in Economics scores ($M=75.47$) indicates that the higher secondary students are having high Achievement in Economics. There is significant difference between male and female Higher Secondary students with respect to their Achievement in Economics. There is no significant difference between rural and urban, Day scholar and Hostel staying, Government and Aided Higher Secondary school students with respect to their Achievement in Economics.

Key Words: Achievement Test, Economics and Higher Secondary Students

Introduction:

Education competence in the present world is interwoven with the progress of every society. Educationists have sensitized people in comprehending that education serves as knowledge inputs, for the individual to use his potentials as a vital resource, in the direction of progress to meet the demands of the society. Learning in a classroom depends a great deal on the structure and pattern of inter-personal relationship particularly pupil-pupil relationship, existing at a given point of time within the learning group. According to the modern concept of education, best adjustment is the ultimate goal of education. The most significant agency of education is school, where an individual should learn to adjust. Good adjustment makes the students proud and self- satisfaction motivates them for future success, encourages them to be of independent thinking and builds their self- confidence.

Academic Achievement assumes primary importance in the context of an education system aimed at progressive scholastic development of the child and human resources development at the macro level. The scientific rearing and education of a child is monitored on the basis of his academic achievement. Academic achievement is the core of the wider term i.e. educational growth. The importance of academic achievement in one's life cannot be over emphasized. It acts as an emotional tonic. Sound academic records are the pillars on which the entire future personality stands. Academic achievement have always been the centre of educational research and despite varied definitions about the aims of education, the academic development of the child continue to be the primary and most important goal of education . Life in general and for a student in particular has become highly competitive. Today there is no place for a mediocre student. There is limited room at the top that too only for the best. The importance of scholastic and academic achievement has raised important questions for educational researchers. What factors promote achievement in students? How far do the different factors contribute towards academic achievement? (Ramaswamy, 1990). In this context, the role of socioeconomic status cannot be denied as it has a great effect on personality, learning and development of the individual and his academic achievement.

Need and Importance of this Study:

It is known that several environmental factors too, influence the pupils' academic achievements. In the normal Indian classroom climate, teachers have to teach students hailing from socio-cultural and economic backgrounds. This naturally leads to a number of problems in instruction, the factors influences teaching and learning process. Hence the instigator decided to take up this study.

Objectives of the Study:

The present study has the following objectives:-

- To find out the Higher Secondary Students' level of achievement in Economics.
- To find out whether there is any significant difference between the selected pairs of sub samples in respective of higher secondary students' achievement in economics.

Hypotheses:

Suitable hypotheses were framed

Method of Study:

The present investigation was undertaken by using normative survey method.

Tools Used:

Achievement Test in Economics constructed and validated by the Investigator.

Statistical Techniques:

In this present investigation the following statistical techniques were used.

Descriptive Analysis:

- Measures of central tendency (Mean)
- Measures of variability (Standard Deviation)

Differential Analysis:

- Independent Sample ‘t’ test

Sample of the Study:

The present study consists of 1060 higher secondary students studying in Tirunelveli District of Tamil Nadu state. The sample was selected by using simple random sampling technique. The sample forms a representative sample of the entire population. Due proportionate weightage was given to various sub-samples.

Descriptive and Differential Analysis:

Analysis of Mean achievement in Economics scores of higher secondary students with respect to their Gender:

Null Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference between Male and Female Higher Secondary students with respect to their achievement in Economics. In order to test the above Null hypothesis ‘t’ value is calculated.

Table 1: Significance of difference between Mean Achievement in Economics scores of higher secondary students with respect to their Gender

Sub -Samples	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Significance at 0.05 Level
Male	460	108.14	23.31	3.67	Significant
Female	600	102.78	16.34		

From the above table, since the ‘t’ value is significant at 0.05 level , the above null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that there is significant difference between the male and female Higher Secondary School students with respect to their Achievement in Economics.

Analysis of Mean achievement in Economics scores of higher secondary students with respect to their Locality:

Null Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference between Rural and Urban Higher Secondary students with respect to their achievement in Economics. In order to test the above Null hypothesis ‘t’ value is calculated.

Table 2: Significance of difference between Mean Achievement in Economics scores of higher secondary students with respect to their Locality

Sub-Samples	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Significance at 0.05 level
Rural	560	75.06	11.48	1.29	Not significant
Urban	500	75.93	10.48		

From the above table, since the ‘t’ value is not significant at 0.05 level , the above null hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that there is no significant difference between Rural and Urban Higher Secondary students with respect to their achievement in Economics.

Analysis of Mean achievement in Economics scores of higher secondary students with respect to the Type of Institution:

Null Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference between Government and Aided Higher Secondary School students with respect to their achievement in Economics. In order to test the above Null hypothesis ‘t’ value is calculated.

Table 3: Significance of difference between Mean Achievement in Economics scores of higher secondary students with respect to the Type of Institution

Sub-Samples	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Significance at 0.05 level
Govt.	571	75.82	11.07	1.12	Not significant
Aided	489	75.06	10.97		

From the above table, since the ‘t’ value is not significant at 0.05 level , the above null hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that there is no significant difference between the Government and Aided Higher Secondary School students with respect to their achievement in Economics.

Analysis of Mean Achievement in Economics scores of higher secondary students with respect to their place of stay:

Null Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference between Home and Hostel staying Higher Secondary students with respect to their achievement in Economics. In order to test the above Null hypothesis ‘t’ value is calculated.

Table 4: Significance of difference between Mean Achievement in Economics scores of higher secondary students with respect to their place of stay

Sub-Samples	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Significance at 0.05 level
Hostel	152	74.56	10.95	1.09	Not significant
Home	908	75.62	11.03		

From the above table, since the 't' value is not significant at 0.05 level, the above null hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that there is no significant difference between Home and Hostel staying Higher Secondary students with respect to their achievement in Economics.

Analysis of Mean Achievement in Economics scores of higher secondary students with respect to their family type:

Null Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference between Nuclear and Joint family Higher Secondary students with respect to their achievement in Economics. In order to test the above Null hypothesis 't' value is calculated.

Table 5: Significance of difference between Mean Achievement in Economics scores of higher secondary students with respect to their family type

Sub-Samples	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Significance at 0.05 level
Nuclear	435	74.86	11.53	1.47	Not significant
Joint	625	75.89	10.65		

From the above table, since the 't' value is not significant at 0.05 level, the above null hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that there is no significant difference between Nuclear and Joint family Higher Secondary students with respect to their achievement in Economics.

Findings of the Study:

- The Achievement in Economics of entire sample of Higher Secondary Students is high.
- There is significant difference between the male and female Higher Secondary School students with respect to their Achievement in Economics.
- There is no significant difference between Rural and Urban Higher Secondary students with respect to their achievement in Economics.
- There is no significant difference between the Government and Aided Higher Secondary School students with respect to their achievement in Economics.
- There is no significant difference between Day scholar and Hostel staying Higher Secondary students with respect to their achievement in Economics.
- There is no significant difference between Nuclear and Joint family Higher Secondary students with respect to their achievement in Economics.

Recommendations:

- The study shows that the Female students are having higher achievement than male students; this trend was observed in this whole decade, hence special attention is to be extended upon male students to increase their achievement. Further no other discriminations shows differences in achievement in Economics, hence, no need to show any kind of differences in methodology of teaching on the basis of sub variables taken for this study.
- Further all the independent variables shows significant relationship with achievement in Economics and also among each other, hence, Educators should give proper importance to these variables while framing curriculum.
- The study also reveals that the students do not differ significantly in their achievement in Social Science. So the teachers working in government and private schools should maintain the present way of teaching the Social Science.

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